

UTILIZATION OF E-RESOURCES AND ACADEMIC ACHIEVEMENT AMONG UNDERGRADUATE STUDENTS

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ABSTRACT

The paper aims to assess and evaluate the exposure of Information and Communication Technology (ICT) and the use of e-resources by the Under Graduate (UG) student of Colleges of Chirang district of Assam. Besides, it aims to highlight the problems encountered by the students and suggests remedial measures for its improvement. The investigator has author investigated the use of e-resources through a survey based on a structured questionnaire. The study confirmed that students of UG level in Chirang District are aware of the e-resources and use various types of e-resources, e-database, and e-journals. It suggests for the improvement in the access facilities with high internet speed and subscription of more e-resources for the students.

Keywords: ICT, e-resources, e-journal, internet

INTRODUCTION

E-resources are those resources which include documents in electronic or e-format that can be accessed via Internet in digital library environment. E-resources are that electronic product that delivers a collection of data, be it text, image collection, other multimedia products like numerical, graphical mode for commercially available for library and information centre's. These may be delivered on CD-ROM / DVD, over the Internet and so on. Providing access to e-Resources is a service to help academic library users to find E – databases, E- journals, E- Magazines, E-Books, E-Audio, E-Images, Data, GIS, Digital Library Projects, Electronic Exhibitions, E-Subject Guide, E-newsletters, E-White papers, E-conferences proceedings and Web search tools on a range of topic. Many of the electronic resources are freely available to anyone over Internet access but some are commercial resources. "Social media has the most diverse features and characteristics of recent form of media. It includes many features like communicating, texting, images sharing, video and audio sharing, connecting with word's friend both known and unknown" (Basumatary, D & Kumar S., 2020). There are moral deterioration and degradation that are prevailing in every sphere of life. Therefore, there is an urgent need to rebuild our nation starting from the grass root level and by means of educating our children (Basumatary, D & Thiumai, E., 2019). Social media has a great role in building personality to update current information and exchange of idea. But all the information are always not true. The information which does not have an authentic value cannot be helpful for the students. The individual, who doesn't have power to judge that, what is right and what is wrong, they may be misguided.

Operational terms defined:

1. **E-resources:** E-resources is short term for Electronic Resources or electronic information resources. These are collections of information in electronic or digital format that are accessed on an electronic device, such as a mobile phone, computer, etc.
2. **Educational blogs:** An education blog is a blog created for educational purposes. Edublogs archive and support student and teacher learning by facilitating reflection, questioning by self and others, collaboration and by providing contexts for engaging in higher-order thinking.
3. **Under graduate students:** Students of college level, Involved in or undertaking study at an advanced level after having Higher Secondary (HS) from a School or college.
4. **Attitude:** the way a person views something or tends to behave towards it, often in an evaluative way
5. **E-journals:** Electronic journals, also known as e-journals, e-journals, and electronic serials, are scholarly journals or intellectual magazines that can be accessed via electronic transmission. In practice, this means that they are usually published on the Web.

LITERATURE REVIEW

Various studies have been carried out regarding to the exposure of computers and e-resources to the students, research scholars and teachers of various institutions and universities. Swain & Panda in their study observed that faculty members prefer using e-articles, e-thesis and dissertation over to their printed counterparts. The Internet, e-mail, and e-resources are utilized by various organisations in India. The usage and usability of e-journal is studied by Satpathy & Rout, reveals that faculty members are aware of the e-resources. The online access to full-text journals in the area of agriculture and veterinary sciences are being provided to the students, researchers, and teachers by the Indian Council of Agriculture Research (ICAR)

1. Level & Myers (2003) opined that collection development activities are an important and ongoing component in every library. Digitization of paper driven environment is on the rise. The introduction of the web and the internet into the collection development has increased the level of efficiency and accessibility manifold by integrating procedures, forms, policies and library organization web sites.
2. Pragyana Das et.al (2007) stated that “collection management can also be defined as the organization and maintenance of library resources, starting from collection development principle”.
3. Linda M.Teel (2008) described an inventory project conducted in the East Carolina University Teaching Resource Center, North Carolina, USA to review the relevancy, accuracy, reliability and circulation of curriculum collection. This case study discussed significant outcomes that were accomplished and implemented for long range strategic planning
4. Rubinandhini (2012) has conducted a survey on collection development in Periyar University Library, Tamil Nadu. Her findings have revealed that their university library provides many printed and e-resource facilities to its users. The university library is playing a vital role in innovations of exploring new concepts to help the society at large.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

The objectives of the study are to:

1. To expose the use of ICT in the colleges of Chirang District.
2. To identify use and purpose of internet services in libraries.
3. To explore the use of e-resources by the UG students of Chirang district colleges.
4. To examine the attitude of the students of the university towards use of e-resources.

METHODOLOGY

This study is based on survey method and questionnaire tool. A structured questionnaire was designed to collect data from the UG students of Chirang district colleges, keeping in mind the basic objectives of the study. The data was collected from the students during the educational settings of College, National and Central Library of different colleges of Chirang district.

DELIMITATIONS

This study is delimited within the UG level students of Chirang district of Assam.

Analysis & Interpretation of data: The collected information from the data was analyzed statistically by using SPSS version 20. Following are the inferences ascertained.

Table No. 1:

Students	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig
UG	120	3.54	2.12	735.369	0.000*

*significant at 0.05 level

The above table reveals that attitude towards use of e resources in UG students (N=120), Mean 3.54, Standard Deviation 2.12 and calculated t-value 735.369 and obtained significant value is 0.000 which is significant at 0.05 level.

Table No. 2:

Students	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig
Science	54	1.98	0.876	0.674	0.342
Arts	66	1.97	0.988	0.684	0.359

The above table shows that UG students of Science (N=54), Mean 1.98, Standard Deviation 0.876 and calculated t-value 0.675 and obtained significant value is 0.342, Arts (N=66) Mean 1.97, Standard Deviation 0.988 and calculated t-value 0.684 and obtained significant value is 0.339 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore above stated hypothesis is rejected.

Table No. 3:

Students	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig
Girls	55	1.98	0.576	0.575	0.342
Boys	65	1.67	0.708	0.580	0.339

The above table shows that under graduate students of Girls (N=55), Mean 1.98, SD 0.576, and calculated t-value 0.575 and obtained significant value is 0.342, Boys (N=65) Mean 1.67, Standard Deviation 0.708 and calculated t-value 0.580 and obtained significant value is 0.339 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore above stated hypothesis is rejected.

Table 6:

Students	N	Mean	SD	t	Sig
Rural	70	1.81	0.775	0.612	0.510
Urban	50	1.90	0.824	0.631	0.551

The above table shows that UG students of Rural (N=70), Mean 1.81, Standard Deviation 0.775 and calculated t-value 0.612 and obtained significant value is 0.510, Urban (N=50) Mean 1.824, Standard Deviation 0.824 and calculated t-value 0.631 and obtained significant value is 0.551 which is not significant at 0.05 level. Therefore above stated hypothesis is rejected.

Conclusion:

The study has been found that most of the UG students of Chirang district has neutral attitude towards using e-resources in their learning. It is important to look after the use of resources that to develop the available facilities being provided to the students in the university. On the other hand, it also revealed that practical uses of e-resources are not up to the worth in comparison to investments made in acquiring these resources. Furthermore, for improved usage of e-resources across campus, infrastructure and training programmes are required.

Suggestions:

1. User training is essential for the better use of e-resources in the library since a good number of users are searching electronic literature on their own.
2. The library of the university should identify the below average users and convert them into potential users of the resources.
3. The university management should provide funds for subscription to more electronic sources.
4. Further users are coming across with problems in gathering information, the most suitable measures should be taken to overcome this.
5. Finally, there is a need for the institutional governing body to integrate adequate information regarding usage of e-resources for both student and teachers in the university.

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